

Mechanistic insight into oxidative degradation of some azo dyes with kinetic and thermodynamic analysis

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Abstract : In this paper, an attempt has been made to get a kinetic and mechanistic insight into the oxidative degradation of azo dyes, Acid Red-14 and Acid Red-26 by hexacyanoferrate, abbreviated as HCF(III) ions spectrophotometrically at λ_{\max} of reaction mixture 515 and 507 nm respectively. The effect of various operational parameters such as the concentration of dye, oxidant, and solution pH on the reaction rate has been determined. The results show that the reaction follows first order kinetics with respect to [HCF(III)] and [Dye]. Thermodynamic parameters have been evaluated by studying the reaction rate at four different temperatures; 40 °C to 55 °C. Based on the experimental results a plausible reaction mechanism involving complex formation has been proposed and rate law has been derived. The degradation products were extracted by ethyl acetate and identified by LC-MS.

Keywords : Kinetic, degradation, Acid Red-14, Acid Red-26, HCF(III).

Introduction

The discharge of wastewaters from textile industries, pulp mills and dyestuff manufacturing has provoked serious environmental concerns all over the world¹⁻³. Colour is the first contaminant to be recognized in the wastewater. The presence of very small amounts of dyes in water (less than 1 ppm for some dyes) is highly visible and aesthetically unpleasant⁴. Dyes are complex aromatic compounds, which are normally used for coloration of various substrates like leather, textiles, papers, etc. They are sometimes fused with heavy metals on the structural interface and are considered to have relatively bad consequence on the surrounding environment due to their toxic and inhibitory nature⁵. In addition, several classes of dyes especially azo dyes are stable molecules that are resistant to degradation by light, chemical, biological and other exposures and are considered as possible carcinogens or mutagens to humans^{6,7}. Therefore, it is necessary to reduce dye concentration in the wastewater before it is released into marine environment.

Hexacyanoferrate(III) is a mild oxidant which attacks the organic compound at a particular stage. It abstracts only one electron from the substrate yielding a simple step in any reaction mechanism; and being a one electron

oxidant with a redox potential of +0.45 V of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}/\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$ couple in alkaline medium, the oxidant exhibits appreciable stability in solution and yields a stable reduction product hexacyanoferrate(II)^{8,9}. Hexacyanoferrate(III), has been widely used to oxidize numerous organic and inorganic compounds in alkaline media^{10,11}. Recently, Goel *et al.* have extended the oxidation capability of HCF(III) to the degradation of methyl orange¹². In continuation of this work, the present study deals with the redox chemistry of HCF(III) in alkaline medium and highlights the kinetics of oxidation of azo dyes, Acid Red-14 (AR-14) and Acid Red-26 (AR-26) by HCF(III) and helps in proposing a suitable mechanism for the oxidation of azo dyes by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) ions on the basis of kinetic and thermodynamic results (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Structure of AR-14 and AR-26.

Experimental

All the chemicals and reagents used in the study were of AR grade. pH of the reaction mixture was adjusted by using KH_2PO_4 and NaOH as buffer. The kinetic experiments were carried out as reported earlier^{13,14} by mixing the required quantity of HCF(III), buffer and water in an iodine flask kept at the same temperature and stirred a little with the help of the pipette. The reaction mixture and stock solution of dye was then clamped separately in a thermostat at 40 ± 0.1 °C. After about half an hour, a required amount of dye solution was added to the mixture and stirred to start the reaction. The progress of the reaction was measured spectrophotometrically. Aliquots were withdrawn from the reaction mixture after repeated intervals of 5 min and the absorbance were recorded. The absorbance vs time plots were made for all the sets. The initial rate method was used to decide the kinetic behaviour of the reaction. Initial rates $(da/dt)_i$ were evaluated after 5 min from the start of the reaction by using plane mirror method from the plot of absorbance (a) vs time (t). The best fitting curve were obtained by the method of least square. The first order rate constant was calculated by the plot of $\log(a-x)$ vs time with slope equal to $-k_1/2.303$.

The products were extracted by ethyl acetate and identified by LCMS. The mobile phase for extracted product of AR-14 consisted of methanol : water : acetonitrile (25 : 50 : 25) and that for extracted product of AR-26 was acetonitrile : water (60 : 40).

Results and discussion

In order to investigate the mechanism of oxidation, the kinetic behaviour of AR-14 and AR-26 has been studied at constant pH and temperature at different concentrations of one reactant keeping the concentration of others constant.

Effect of pH :

pH is one of the most important operating parameters that affect the degradation of organic compounds. The effect of pH was studied by varying it from 6–10.5 for AR-14 and AR-26 respectively (Tables 1 and 2) because above these pH, the colour of both dyes changes. The rate of degradation was found to be maximum at pH 6 and 9 for AR-14 and AR-26 respectively. The study reveals that though the reaction rate of AR-14 is maximum

Table 1. Effect of variation of pH, [AR-14], [HCF(III)] on the rate of degradation of AR-14 at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 515$ nm, Temp. = 40 ± 0.1 °C

pH	[AR-14] $\times 10^5$ (mol dm ⁻³)	[HCF(III)] $\times 10^6$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$(da/dt) \times 10^3$ (min ⁻¹)
6.0	3.0	3.0	2.0
6.5	3.0	3.0	1.6
7.0	3.0	3.0	1.2
7.5	3.0	3.0	0.6
7.5	1.0	3.0	0.2
7.5	2.0	3.0	0.4
7.5	3.0	3.0	0.6
7.5	4.0	3.0	1.0
7.5	5.0	3.0	1.4
7.5	6.0	3.0	1.8
7.5	7.0	3.0	2.2
7.5	8.0	3.0	2.6
7.5	3.0	1.0	0.2
7.5	3.0	2.0	0.4
7.5	3.0	3.0	0.6
7.5	3.0	4.0	0.9
7.5	3.0	5.0	1.0
7.5	3.0	6.0	1.2
7.5	3.0	7.0	1.4
7.5	3.0	8.0	1.5
7.5	3.0	9.0	1.6

Table 2. Effect of variation of pH, [AR-26], [HCF(III)] on the rate of degradation of AR-26 at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 507$ nm, Temp. = 40 ± 0.1 °C

pH	[AR-26] $\times 10^5$ (mol dm ⁻³)	[HCF(III)] $\times 10^6$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$(da/dt) \times 10^3$ (min ⁻¹)
6.0	3.0	3.0	1.0
6.5	3.0	3.0	0.6
7.0	3.0	3.0	0.6
7.5	3.0	3.0	0.8
8.0	3.0	3.0	1.2
8.5	3.0	3.0	1.4
9.0	3.0	3.0	1.6
9.5	3.0	3.0	1.4
10.0	3.0	3.0	1.2
10.5	3.0	3.0	1.0
9.0	1.0	3.0	0.4
9.0	2.0	3.0	0.6
9.0	3.0	3.0	1.4
9.0	4.0	3.0	2.0
9.0	5.0	3.0	2.8
9.0	6.0	3.0	3.6

Table-2 (contd.)

9.0	7.0	3.0	4.4
9.0	8.0	3.0	5.6
9.0	3.0	1.0	0.6
9.0	3.0	2.0	0.8
9.0	3.0	3.0	1.2
9.0	3.0	4.0	1.6
9.0	3.0	5.0	2.0
9.0	3.0	6.0	2.2
9.0	3.0	7.0	2.4
9.0	3.0	8.0	2.6
9.0	3.0	9.0	3.0

at pH 6.0, 7.0 has been chosen as the optimum pH as per the requirement of the experimental conditions. At high pH values, the rate of degradation may decline due to columbic repulsion between anionic dye surface and hydroxyl anion, hence they do not have opportunity to react with dye molecules¹⁵.

Effect of HCF(III) :

The kinetic results presented in Tables 1 and 2 show that oxidation of AR-14 and AR-26 follows first order kinetics with respect to [HCF(III)]. The concentration of HCF(III) was varied from 1×10^{-6} to 9×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³.

Effect of [substrate] :

The effect of substrate concentration on reaction rate

was studied by varying its concentration from 1×10^{-5} to 8×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³. The data presented in Tables 1 and 2 show first order dependence of rate on the concentration of substrate.

Thermodynamic parameters :

The thermodynamic parameters for oxidation of both dyes AR-14 and AR-26 (shown in Table 3) have been evaluated by studying the reaction at four different temperatures in the range of 40 to 55 °C. The degradation of both the dyes follows Arrhenius rate law for reactions in solutions. The high value of activation energy (E_a) and high value of frequency factor (A) reveals low rate of degradation of both the dyes under the experimental conditions. Negative entropy (ΔS^\ddagger) of activation shows the formation of polar species during the reaction. Energy of formation (ΔF^\ddagger) is almost same for both the reactions suggesting similar mechanism involved during the reaction. The Arrhenius equation is mentioned as follows :

$$K = Ae^{-E_a/RT}$$

Identification of degradation products :

Degradation of azo dyes were monitored by UV-Vis spectroscopy (Fig. 2a and b). AR-14 is characterized by maximum absorption at 515 nm attributed to the chromophore containing azo linkage of the dye molecule in the solution¹⁶. The disappearance of this band and forma-

Fig. 2. UV-Vis spectra of (a) AR-14 and extracted product (b) AR-26 and extracted product.

Table 3. Thermodynamic parameters

Parameter	Values	
	AR-14	AR-26
E_a (kcal mol ⁻¹)	14.9	15.7
ΔH^\ddagger (kcal mol ⁻¹)	14.3	15.1
ΔS^\ddagger (e.u.)	-14.3	-9.6
ΔF^\ddagger (kcal mol ⁻¹)	18.9	18.2
A (L mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	1.37×10^{10}	1.439×10^{11}

tion of new bands at 250 and 268 nm supports the degradation. The absorption maximum for AR-26 is observed at 507 nm. Here also, it can be seen that the extracted product forms the bands at 245, 273 nm leading to degradation of the dye. In order to provide supported evidences for degradation, identification of degradation products was carried out by LC-MS. 1-Hydroxy-2-amino naphthalene, naphthalene sodium sulphate and 2-(3'-hydroxy)- benzene

ethanoic acid, 2-(2',5'-dihydroxy)benzene ethanoic acid have been identified as the major degradation products for AR-14 and AR-26 respectively. The results of LC-MS are shown in Fig. 3 (a and b). Proposed chemical structures of the expected degradation products for AR-14 and AR-26 are listed in Table 4.

Mechanism :

Based on the above kinetic, thermodynamic data, LC-MS analysis and previously reported work :

It is assumed that dye (D) molecule exist as an anion (D⁻) in the alkaline medium which forms complex with

Fig. 3. LC-MS of degraded products of (a) AR-14 and (b) AR-26.

Molecular weight	Proposed structure For AR-14
159	<p>1-Hydroxy-2-amino naphthalene</p>
353	<p>3-Naphthyl-4-hydroxy naphthalene sulphonic acid</p>
170	<p>2-(2',5'-Dihydroxy)benzene ethanoic acid</p>
153	<p>2-(3'-Hydroxy)benzene ethanoic acid</p>

HCF(III)¹⁷. This complex dissociates through a slow step into product and Fe(CN)₆⁴⁻. Based on the above mechanism and experimental facts, the following rate law has been derived :

$$r = k_1K [D^-][HCF(III)]$$

which is similar to experimental rate law

$$R_{obs} = k[D^-][HCF(III)]$$

where, $k = k_1K$

Conclusion

Degradation of azo dyes, AR-14 and AR-26 was investigated spectrophotometrically by HCF(III) which proved its ability as potential oxidant for the removal of dyes. The oxidative degradation kinetics of both the dyes by HCF(III) follow first order kinetic model with respect to [HCF(III)] and [Dye]. The pH of reaction mixture played

a significant role in the degradation of both the azo dyes. A plausible mechanism has been proposed and thermodynamic parameters have been evaluated which supports the derived rate law. 1-Hydroxy-2-amino naphthalene, naphthalene sodium sulphate and 2-(3'-hydroxy)benzene ethanoic acid and 2-(2',5'-dihydroxy)benzene ethanoic acid have been identified as the major degradation products for AR-14 and AR-26 respectively by LC-MS which are less hazardous than azo dyes.

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